

Heterobimetallic triethanolaminate–isopropoxides of alkaline earth metals

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Abstract : Reaction of insoluble homometallic triethanolaminate derivatives $\{M(\text{teaH}_2)_2\}_n$ ($M = \text{divalent Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba}$; $\text{teaH}_3 = \text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3$, $\text{teaH}_2 = (\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2$) [prepared from 1 : 2 reactions of $M(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ with triethanolamine] with $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4 \cdot \text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ in benzene or toluene under refluxing condition afford after usual work-up, hydrocarbon soluble heterobimetallic derivatives of the type $[M(\text{tea})_2\{M'(\text{OPr}^i)_3\}]$ ($M' = \text{tetravalent Ti, Zr}$). All these derivatives, which are comparatively less moisture-sensitive than their parent component metal isopropoxides have been characterized by elemental analyses, spectroscopic [IR, NMR (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{27}Al)] studies and molecular weight measurements.

Keywords : Heterobimetallic alkoxides, alkaline earth metal ion derivatives, triethanolamines.

Introduction

Innovations in synthetic strategies continue to afford many novel heterometal complexes with exceedingly interesting structural features and unique chemical properties¹⁻³. Our previous work concentrated on the use of homometal complexes of glycols and diethanolamines for the synthesis of soluble heterometal complexes of alkaline earth metal ions⁴. Encouraged by the observation of Pfalzgraf and coworkers⁵, regarding the ready dissolution of insoluble $\text{La}(\text{teaH})(\text{teaH}_2)$ in toluene in the presence of $\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_5$, utilizing a similar strategy we have also explored the synthesis of heterobimetallic alkoxide-triethanolamines of a number of other metals⁶.

In the present study, we have extended our interest to the synthesis derivatives of the type $[M(\text{tea})_2\{M(\text{OPr}^i)_3\}]$ ($M = \text{alkaline earth metal ion}$; $M' = \text{tetravalent Ti, Zr}$) and compounds characterization has been done by physicochemical methods.

Results and discussion

Reactions of freshly prepared alkaline earth metal (Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba) isopropoxides with triethanolamine (teaH_3) in 1 : 2 molar ratio in benzene or toluene afford hydrocarbon insoluble homo metal complexes :

Interactions of (A) in benzene under refluxing conditions with $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ or $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ in 1 : 4 molar ratio, yield hydrocarbon soluble, monomeric heterobimetallic complexes according to the following reaction :

(1) : $M = \text{Mg}$, $M' = \text{Ti}$, $n = 0$; (2) : $M = \text{Ca}$, $M' = \text{Ti}$, $n = 0$; (3) : $M = \text{Sr}$, $M' = \text{Ti}$, $n = 0$; (4) : $M = \text{Ba}$, $M' = \text{Ti}$, $n = 0$; (5) : $M = \text{Mg}$, $M' = \text{Zr}$, $n = 1$; (6) : $M = \text{Ca}$, $M' = \text{Zr}$, $n = 1$; (7) : $M = \text{Sr}$, $M' = \text{Zr}$, $n = 1$; (8) : $M = \text{Ba}$, $M' = \text{Zr}$, $n = 1$.

All these derivatives 1–8 (Table 1) are colourless moisture-sensitive solids, soluble in common organic solvents (e.g. benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, dichloromethane, etc.) and depict monomeric nature ebullioscopically in benzene and decompose without melting above 245 °C.

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Spectral studies :

The infrared spectra of the derivatives 1–8 (Table 2) exhibit absorptions (Nujol, cm^{-1}) due to triethanolamine

moieties^{5,6} at 2985–2965 $\nu\text{C-H}$, 1470–1445 $\delta_s \text{CH}_2$ and 870–810 $\nu\text{C-C}$, and for isopropoxy groups at 1164–1100 νOPr^i , 1088–1030 $\nu\text{C-O}$. The absorptions due to metal

Table 1. Analytical and some physical data for complexes 1–8

Compd. ^a M/M'	Yield ^b g (%)	Liberated isopropyl alcohol Found (Calcd.)	Analysis (%) :			M. Wt Found (Calcd.)
			(M = Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba)	Ti/Zr	N	
(1) Mg/Ti	2.69 (96)	0.55 (0.54)	2.09 (1.99)	15.39 (15.73)	2.29 (2.30)	1250 (1217)
(2) Ca/Ti	5.0 (93)	0.99 (0.98)	3.20 (3.24)	15.70 (15.53)	2.20 (2.27)	1200 (1233)
(3) Sr/Ti	3.0 (89)	0.59 (0.57)	6.86 (6.84)	14.76 (14.95)	2.21 (2.10)	1296 (1281)
(4) Ba/Ti	3.54 (91)	0.66 (0.65)	10.32 (10.33)	14.52 (14.39)	2.21 (2.10)	1360 (1330)
(5) Mg/Zr	3.57 (93)	1.25 (1.24)	1.83 (1.74)	26.46 (26.24)	2.10 (2.01)	1420 (1390)
(6) Ca/Zr	5.0 (87)	1.72 (1.71)	2.77 (2.84)	22.84 (22.94)	1.84 (1.99)	1440 (1406)
(7) Sr/Zr	2.81 (88)	1.00 (0.93)	6.20 (6.02)	25.21 (25.09)	2.10 (2.92)	
(8) Ba/Zr	4.20 (94)	1.54 (1.53)	10.40 (10.36)	27.51 (27.53)	2.20 (2.11)	

^aAll are moisture-sensitive colourless solids.

^bYield refers to recrystallized product.

Table 2. Structurally significant infrared absorptions (cm^{-1}) for derivatives $[\text{M}(\text{tea}_2)_2\{(\text{M}'(\text{OPr}^i)_3)_4\}]$ (1)–(8)

Compd. M/M'	$\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{OPr}^i)$	(C-O)	$\nu(\text{M-O})^a$ $[\nu(\text{M}'\text{-O})]^a$	$\nu(\text{M-N})^a$
(1) Mg/Ti	1280m	1129s, 1115s	1037m	515m (Mg-O) [539m, Ti-O]	314w
(2) Ca/Ti	1251m	1129s, 1100s	1030m	484m (Ca-O) [529m, Ti-O]	303w
(3) Sr/Ti	1258m	1164s, 1114s	1088m	470m (Sr-O) [530m, Ti-O]	287w
(4) Ba/Ti	1266m	1164s, 1112s	1073m	425m (Ba-O) [529m, Ti-O]	278w
(5) Mg/Zr	1266m	1129s, 1100s	1030m	510m (Mg-O) [544m, Zr-O]	320w
(6) Ca/Zr	1276m	1158s, 1112s	1036m	482m (Ca-O) [536m, Zr-O]	310w
(7) Sr/Zr	1258m	1158s, 1112s	1080m	472m (Ba-O) [543m, Zr-O]	285w
(8) Ba/Zr	1251m	1151s, 1115s	1038m	430m (Ba-O) [544m, Zr-O]	275w

^aIn addition to the absorptions listed herein a number of weak absorptions are also observed.

Table 3. ^1H NMR spectral data^a (δ ppm) for derivatives 1–8

(1)	1.15 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.83 (12H, br, NCH_2), 3.83 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.20 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(2)	1.17 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.70 (12H, br, NCH_2), 3.67 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.05 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(3)	1.23 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.70 (12H, br, NCH_2), 3.65 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.20 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(4)	1.18 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.70 (12H, br, NCH_2), 3.73 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.40 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(5)	1.25 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.72 (12H, br, NCH_2), 3.73 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.40 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(6)	1.23 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.66 (12H, br, NCH_2), 4.20 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.84 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(7)	1.21 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.66 (12H, br, NCH_2), 4.20 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.84 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)
(8)	1.18 (72H, d, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2), 2.75 (12H, br, NCH_2), 3.70 (12H, br, OCH_2), 4.0 (12H, Sept, J 6.15 Hz, CHMe_2)

^aRecorded in CDCl_3 with TMS as an internal reference.

oxygen mode appear in the regions 575–530 (M' = tetravalent Ti, Zr) and 515–425 (M = divalent Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba). The absorptions observed in the region 315–275 may be assigned to $\nu\text{M} \leftarrow \text{N}$ (M = divalent Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba) mode^{6a}.

The ^1H NMR spectral data for 1–8 along with their assignments based on the published data^{5,6}, are listed in Table 3. The signals for NCH_2 and OCH_2 protons exhibit a deshielding of ~ 0.03 – 0.12 and 0.01 – 0.16 ppm respectively. Isopropoxy groups in these derivatives (1)–(8) appear in the regions : δ 1.15–1.25 (CHMe_2) and 4.04–4.84 (OCHMe_2).

Plausible structure :

The structure shown in Fig. 1 is mainly based on the following considerations :

(i) The structural elucidation of $[\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})\text{-(C}_2\text{H}_4\text{OH)}_2]_2\text{Ba}\cdot 2\text{EtOH}$ ⁷ and $[\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}_3\text{La}\{\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4\}_3\text{-N}\}_2$ ⁵ by X-ray crystallography.

(ii) The well established tetradentate encapsulating ligating mode of triethanolamine (teaH_3) and its deprotonated anionic forms³.

(iii) The coordination number of divalent Mg is predominantly 6 (only in a few cases 5, 7 and 8 coordination are known). The heavier alkaline earth metal (Ca, Sr, Ba) ions exhibit coordination numbers 7 and 8, the latter is predominant in complexes derived from polydentate ligands⁸.

(iv) The observed analytical, molecular weight, and spectroscopic data.

Experimental

All reactions and subsequent manipulations were performed under rigorous anhydrous conditions, using oven

O \dashrightarrow M connectivity presumably of non-existence for $M = \text{Mg}$ (M = divalent Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba; M' = tetravalent Ti, Zr)

Fig. 1. Proposed structure for the derivatives (1)–(8).

dried (130–150 °C) glass apparatus fitted with standard interchangeable quickfit joints (B_{24} , B_{19} cones and sockets). Procedures for drying reagent grade solvents, preparation and purification of starting materials and new compounds, methods for elemental analyses, estimation of liberated isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope, and physical methods employed for characterization of new compounds were the same as described in some of our earlier publications^{4,6}.

Due to similarity in preparative procedures for the new derivatives and also for the sake of brevity, preparative details only for one derivative is given below :

Synthesis of $[\{\text{Pr}^i\text{O}\}_3\text{Ti}\}_4\text{Mg}(\text{tea})_2$ (1) :

After addition of $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (2.59 g, 8.8 mmol) to the well stirred suspension of freshly prepared $\text{Mg}(\text{teaH}_2)_2$ (0.73 g, 2.2 mmol) in toluene (60 ml), the reaction mixture was refluxed under a fractionating column for ~ 12 h, with continuous azeotropic removal and collection of the liberated isopropyl alcohol. When liberation of isopropyl alcohol ceased off, the solution was allowed to

cool to room temperature. Removal of the volatile components from the solution under reduced pressure yielded a colourless product (2.69 g, 98% yield), which was recrystallized from a (2 : 1) mixture of *n*-hexane and toluene at -20 °C to get analytically pure compound in 96% yield.

Adopting a procedure similar to **1**, analytically pure compounds **2–8** were prepared from appropriate reactants in desired amount (g, mmol) as given below for each compound :

(2) Ca(teaH₂)₂ [1.33 g, 4.1 mmol] and Ti(OPrⁱ)₄ [4.67 g, 16.4 mmol].

(3) Sr(teaH₂)₂ [0.91 g, 2.3 mmol] and Ti(OPrⁱ)₄ [3.71 g, 9.2 mmol].

(4) Ba(teaH₂)₂ [1.17 g, 2.7 mmol] and Ti(OPrⁱ)₄ [3.09 g, 10.8 mmol].

(5) Mg(teaH₂)₂ [0.83 g, 2.5 mmol] and Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH [4.01 g, 10.0 mmol].

(6) Ca(teaH₂)₂ [1.20 g, 3.5 mmol] and Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH [5.53 g, 14.0 mmol]

(7) Sr(teaH₂)₂ [0.74 g, 1.9 mmol] and Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH [3.02 g, 7.5 mmol].

(8) Ba(teaH₂)₂ [0.81 g, 3.1 mmol] and Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH [4.95 g, 12.4 mmol].

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